

ZERO-SHOT OPEN SET OBJECT DETECTION IN MUSIC ALBUM COVERS

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ABSTRACT

We applied zero-shot object detection to music album cover art enabling a quantitative iconographic analysis of visual Pop music culture. For this we constructed and partly manually annotated a dataset of decades of USA Billboard chart music. We first used automatic image captioning to yield candidate object classes. Next we input these object classes and the album cover images to a pre-trained zero-shot object classification model, allowing detection of objects and their classes without any re-training. We confirmed accuracy of our approach on a manually labeled sub sample of our dataset. Our results give an overview of what different objects are depicted on album covers belonging to different music genres and types of artists.

1. INTRODUCTION AND RELATED WORK

Our work presents an iconographic approach applied to album covers of Western Pop music. 'Pop' as a genre originated in its modern form during the 1950s in the USA and UK and today encompasses any type of music that a person has been exposed to by the mass media [1]. While the exact definition is subject to constant change and evolution it is clear that Pop music is a multi-modal socio-cultural phenomenon consisting of a rich blend of audio, visual and cultural connotations [2]. Iconography in art studies the visual content of artworks to determine their motifs and themes and to characterize the way these are represented [3]. Iconographic analysis characterizes the way in which themes are represented in images, the number of subjects or objects and their mutual relations, trying to interpret their semantic meaning. Music cover artwork has long been acknowledged to represent a visual genre in its own right and to play an important role in conveying artists' messages and shaping their overall public image [4]. For many genres of Pop music a certain visual aesthetic is a defining characteristic, e.g. cowboy clothes for country music or "demonic" objects like skulls for metal music.

We focused on analyzing music album covers through object detection and to the best of our knowledge, our work presented here is one of the very few approaches to computational analysis of music album covers at scale. Generally speaking, album cover artwork analysis can be seen

as the process of detecting, localizing, or identifying visual elements present in album covers. There is very little research actually analyzing the content within album cover art, with most work using album covers in the context of genre classification. One early example showed [5] that even a rather simple computer vision system can predict music genre from cover artwork or promotional photos to some extent. A more involved multi-modal approach [6] improved genre classification accuracy by combining representations of deep neural networks learned from audio tracks, text reviews, and cover art images. Of specific interest is the authors' attempt to visualize areas of album covers which are important for a classification decisions via so-called "heatmaps" [7]. It could e.g. be shown that the networks rely on detected faces for Rap, Blues, Reggae, R&B, Latin, and World genres, while for Jazz, instruments, typographies and clothes seemed relevant for classification. This result is a clear indication that there is a connection between the music genre and its visual representation in album covers. In addition to other multi-modal approaches [8,9] going beyond image analysis alone, also simple image features have been used to document genre differences in cover art work [10,11].

Since there was no annotated dataset for objects in album covers available, we first created a dataset of Billboard chart music (section 2). Next we applied image captioning to generate detailed descriptions of the album covers and identify representative objects (section 3.1). These captions were then used for an open-set object detection, utilizing a pre-trained model capable of using the generated keywords as labels to detect objects in the images, even if those objects were not part of the labels the model was trained on (section 3.2). As can be seen in the results section 4, open-set object detection allowed more extensive identification of candidate objects across genres and types of artists than image captioning alone. We discuss and conclude our findings in section 5.

2. DATA

To enable analysis of objects visible on music album covers we built the Billboard dataset. This dataset compiles albums ranked as the top-sellers in the USA from 1945 to 2023. The "Billboard 200 Albums" charts select these albums based on sales data, streaming figures, and radio play, reflecting a measure of an album's popularity and commercial success. The data for these albums was obtained from the official Billboard website on most sold al-

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Genre	Albums	(%)	Genre	Albums	(%)
Rock	785	25.08%	Rock And Roll	27	0.863%
Pop	771	24.63%	Christian	27	0.863%
Hip Hop	623	19.90%	Classical	24	0.767%
Country	345	11.02%	Childrens	21	0.671%
RnB	213	6.81%	Christmas	19	0.607%
Electronic	155	4.95%	K-Pop	17	0.543%
Show Tunes	136	4.34%	Comedy	15	0.479%
Soul	129	4.12%	Blues	13	0.415%
Metal	120	3.83%	Easy Listening	12	0.383%
Jazz	77	2.46%	Vocal	8	0.256%
Rap	59	1.89%	Reggae	7	0.224%
Folk	50	1.60%	African	4	0.128%
Various Artists	46	1.47%	Disco	3	0.096%
Funk	43	1.37%	Ballad and Mood Music	1	0.064%
Latin	42	1.34%	Mood Music	1	0.032%
World Music	28	0.90%			

Table 1. Genre distribution in the Billboard dataset, with multiple genres per album possible.

bums¹ from 2002 onward. For years before 2002 data was sourced from Wikipedia². Additional details on genre, artist location, and artist type (male, female, non-binary, various artists or band) was obtained through the Last.fm API³ and the open-source music database, MusicBrainz⁴. We do acknowledge the problematic and vague nature of musical genre (see e.g. [12, 13]), but since it is one of the main organizing principles on music meta information websites, we will make use of it in our analysis of album covers. After eliminating duplicates to account for albums that appeared at the top of the charts in multiple years, the dataset included a total of 3130 unique albums and 31 music genres. Since data from Wikipedia was not complete, there is an uneven distribution of albums across decades, with 82.78% of the albums released from 2000 onward. We are not aware of any systematic bias in the missing data from earlier decades.

In terms of construct validity [14], the dataset and experiments are designed to be representative for music that has been commercially successful in the USA, hence our emphasis is on Western Pop music, which is also evident from looking at the geographic distribution of albums. As expected, the United States is the country with the most albums, accounting for 71.14% of the dataset. This is followed by the United Kingdom, which already represents a significantly smaller proportion at 6.90%. Other countries with a share above one percent are Germany, Canada and Australia. Since the Billboard charts aggregate US music sales information, the whole dataset exhibits a general bias toward English-speaking music. The genre distribution within the dataset, as shown in Table 1, reveals that Rock (25.08%) was the predominant genre, closely followed by Pop (24.63%). It must be noted that an album

can contain more than one music genre. The distribution by artist type indicates that male artists are most prevalent in the dataset, constituting 41.73%, followed by bands at 28.91%, female artists at 17.32%, and "various artists" (referring to albums where multiple artists have collaborated) at 9.04%. It is also worth noting that the "band" category may consist of artists from different genders, though this specific detail is not differentiated in the dataset.

To allow measuring precision of both the image captioning and object detection (see section 4) a smaller subset of the dataset was manually annotated by one of the authors. This "Billboard subset" consists of 346 images (about 10% of the dataset) from the Billboard dataset and was sampled to ensure a distribution of music genres and countries similar to the full dataset.

3. METHODS

Our processing pipeline consists of two major steps: First, image captioning is conducted to extract the most frequent keywords found in album covers, as these words are representative of common objects or elements typically present in album covers (section 3.1). These keywords are then used as inputs for the open-set object detection task, guiding the model to detect relevant objects based on these representative terms (section 3.2). We use a zero-shot object detection model which can detect object classes even if they have not been part of its training data. This model, which has been pre-trained on a large database, can therefore perform object detection without requiring any re-training. It is also able to detect more objects than image captioning alone.

3.1 Image Captioning

For the image captioning process the state-of-the-art model BLIP (Bootstrapping Language-Image Pre-training for Unified Vision-Language Understanding and Generation) [15] was employed to generate image descriptions. The

¹ <https://www.billboard.com/charts/year-end/top-billboard-200-albums/>

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lists_of_Billboard_200_number-one_albums

³ <https://www.last.fm/api>

⁴ <https://musicbrainz.org/>

BLIP model⁵ is designed as a Multi-modal Mixture of Encoder-Decoders (MED). The BLIP encoder processes both text (like captions) and images, creating a unified internal multi-modal representation. The BLIP decoder produces text descriptions for image inputs, enabling tasks such as image captioning. It takes the structured representation from the encoder and transforms it back into human-readable text. For training, BLIP leverages large amounts of noisy image-text pairs from the web. To address the noise inherent in web-crawled data, BLIP employs a process called 'Captioning and Filtering (CapFilt)', essentially first generating captions which are then removed if found inaccurate or irrelevant. The cleaned caption dataset resulting from this process helps train the model to achieve outstanding performance in various applications, like image-text retrieval, image captioning, visual question answering, and zero-shot video-language tasks.

3.2 Zero-shot open set object detection

'Grounding DINO' [16] is an object detection model that can perform open-set detection, where objects can be detected without the model necessarily having been trained on those specific object classes. This model is an improvement on DINO [15] (a DETR-like [17] model), allowing it to connect text descriptions to visual content within images, making it particularly useful for identifying objects not included in the training dataset. Grounding DINO enables to simultaneously process textual and visual data through dedicated encoders. The text encoder, based on a Transformer model like BERT [18], processes textual descriptions into embeddings that represent various semantic attributes or objects. In parallel, the image encoder creates a detailed feature map of the visual input. Feature fusion throughout the modeling pipeline integrates text and image modalities, with an additional language-guided query selection process enhancing the model's focus on relevant parts of the image as indicated by the text, improving the accuracy and relevance of detection results. The key to Grounding DINO's ability to deal with new, unseen classes in a zero-shot setting without re-training lies in its use of language for unseen object generalization. Specifically, the model employs contrastive loss between visual region outputs and language features, enabling the creation of region embeddings that are language-aware. These embeddings allow each region to be classified into new categories inside a language-aware semantic space.

Grounding DINO has demonstrated high performance on benchmarks like COCO, achieving an average precision of 52.5% on the COCO detection zero-shot transfer benchmark without any fine-tuning on COCO [16]. This performance underscores the model's ability to generalize to novel categories effectively.

4. RESULTS

In what follows we will present our results divided into three sections: image captioning using the BLIP model resulting in candidate keywords (section 4.1); choosing

⁵<https://github.com/salesforce/BLIP>

BLIP keywords as input object classes for the Grounding DINO model (section 4.2); zero-shot open set object detection via Grounding DINO on the full Billboard dataset (section 4.3).

4.1 Image captioning

The BLIP model used for automatic captioning was taken from huggingface⁶ and pre-trained on the COCO dataset [19]. Each image from the Billboard dataset was analyzed by models both with and without a so-called captioning seed, which is known to have an influence on the performance. Inspired by the original BLIP paper [15], the seed phrase used was "an album cover that shows", which is then completed by the automatic annotation. Examples of the manual captioning, along with captions generated without and with a seed, are presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. Examples of BLIP recognizing the band (left image), and a hard to describe cover (right image). **Left:** Manual Caption: 'A group of men'. Caption without seed: 'u2 - the singles - the singles'. Caption with seed: 'the band u2 and their band'. **Right:** Manual Caption: 'the eyes of a man and some drawings'. Caption without seed: 'michael jackson - the king of pop'. Caption with seed: 'a man in a tuxedo and a clock'. (The seed mentioned is "an album cover that shows".)

Next we evaluated the image captioning process on the Billboard subset (see section 2), since its manually annotated labels allowed a quantitative comparison with the automatic BLIP captioning. Two metrics were computed in order to evaluate the model's performance: Cosine similarity COS based on Sentence-BERT (S-BERT) and ROUGE. S-BERT is a variation of BERT [18], specifically developed to produce embedding vectors for whole sentences. We compute the cosine similarity between S-BERT [20] embedding vectors of the manually annotated captions and the text generated with and without the seed. The second metric, ROUGE⁷, measures the overlap of unigrams between the automatic and manual annotations. The results for these metrics, both with and without the seed are presented in Table 2. In line with the original BLIP paper [15] the results were decisively better when using the seed. One problem for captioning without a seed is that sometimes a specific album is being recognized, leading to mentioning of the album name and the artist instead of describing

⁶<https://huggingface.co/Salesforce/blip-image-captioning-large>

⁷<https://github.com/google-research/google-research/tree/master/rouge>

Type	COS	ROUGE
Caption without seed	0.465	52.20%
Caption with seed	0.708	72.06%

Table 2. Performance metrics for captioning with and without Seed computed on the Billboard subset. Higher is better for both metrics.

what’s visible in the image (see two examples in figure 1). This is likely due to the specific album cover being part of the model’s training set, causing differences between the manually generated captions and those produced by the model. Additionally, the model occasionally had difficulty with images that are abstract and hard to describe, which is a challenge even for humans (see example on the right in figure 1). As a consequence of these results on the Billboard subset, all subsequent analysis on the full Billboard dataset is using seeded captioning.

4.2 Choosing keywords

Our next step was to distill the most frequent keywords in the captions from the BLIP model when applied to the full Billboard dataset, which will then be used as input to the Grounding DINO model. While the main objective was to identify frequent keywords, we also aimed at recognizing representative words for all different music genres. As indicated in Table 1, there is an imbalance among genres, which might result in the omission of keywords from underrepresented genres. By focusing on the top 20 words from each genre, distinctive words from less frequent genres were also considered, providing a more balanced view of the entire dataset. In addition, cleanup such as removing stop words was performed to focus exclusively on words that refer to detectable objects.

To illustrate our process for choosing keywords for the subsequent classification with the Grounding DINO model, figure 2 shows a genre (x-axis) versus keywords (y-axis) matrix with blue squares indicating that a specific keyword appeared at least once for the corresponding genre. For reasons of limited space this is only shown for 11 of the 31 genres (the 10 most frequent genres plus Latin, as it comes from a different cultural background). Our strategy was to include both keywords applicable to all genres and keywords that are very specific for individual genres. E.g. it can be seen that words like "man", "hat", and "woman" appear consistently across all genres and they were therefore included as input categories for the Grounding DINO model. On the other hand, "leather jacket" was prevalent only in Pop, RnB, and Soul, making it a suitable as a quite specific keyword. Similarly, "cowboy hat" was identified as a representative element for country music. Metal, distinct for its unique vocabulary, included specific words like "skull", "knife", "demon", and "cross". For the RnB genre, "bikini" was a genre-specific term. Musical instruments such as "piano" and "trumpet" were significant in genres like Soul and Jazz, "guitar" can be seen across multiple genres, while "microphone" was notably present in Hip Hop and Soul. Finally, very generic terms such as "person", "clothes", "jeans", "jacket", and

Figure 2. Keyword distribution per genre. Each row represents a word, and each column corresponds to a musical genre. A blue square indicates that a specific word appeared at least once in the corresponding genre, while the absence of a square shows that the word is not associated with that genre.

"pants" were excluded because of their too broad nature. For instance, the word "clothes" is not as informative as specifying the actual garment type. In the same way, using "person" doesn't give as much detail as using "man" or "woman," which can provide more useful insights, like spotting gender trends across different genres or time periods. The 38 classes selected from this analysis and used in Grounding DINO are listed in table 3.

4.3 Zero-shot open set object detection

We used Grounding DINO pre-trained on datasets O365 [21] and GoldG (a combined dataset that includes images from Flickr30k [22] entities and Visual Genome [23]). As has been suggested [16] for the input of keywords derived from the image captioning into the model, we concatenated keywords for each image into strings, separated by periods, like "keyword 1. keyword 2. keyword n.". Only the labels predicted by Grounding DINO were considered for evaluation, disregarding the location of the bounding boxes in the images. Operating in a zero-shot open-set context, without prior training on the Billboard images and classes, Grounding DINO achieved a good performance of mean average precision (mAP, a standard measure in object detection) of 71.53% on the manually annotated Billboard subset. Examples of successful object detection are shown in figure 3, including the bounding boxes for better visibility.

Table 3 shows how often each of the keywords was detected in the full Billboard dataset. Keyword "man" was the most commonly detected class, found in 32.64% of the albums, followed by "woman" in 19.29% of all the objects detected. The keyword "cartoon", which is a sum-

Figure 3. Examples of successful object detection with Grounding DINO.

Class	Freq	%	Class	Freq	%	Class	Freq	%
man	2776	32.64	car	89	1.05	cross	16	0.19
woman	1641	19.30	flowers	87	1.02	motorcycle	13	0.15
cartoon	743	8.74	skull	70	0.82	bed	13	0.15
leatherjacket	461	5.42	beard	65	0.76	piano	10	0.12
suit	375	4.41	chair	47	0.55	gun	10	0.12
blondehair	299	3.52	tie	42	0.49	demon	9	0.11
longhair	294	3.46	dog	42	0.49	boat	8	0.09
hat	281	3.30	microphone	34	0.40	crown	7	0.08
dress	249	2.93	bikini	34	0.40	hoodie	7	0.08
glasses	210	2.47	bird	33	0.39	drawing	6	0.07
tree	177	2.08	table	31	0.36	clock	5	0.06
guitar	135	1.59	street	18	0.21	knife	3	0.04
cowboyhat	112	1.32	trumpet	17	0.20			

Table 3. Distribution of objects detected by Grounding DINO, showing absolute frequency (Freq) and percentage of Billboard dataset (%).

mary term for different drawn graphic elements, appeared in 8.74% of the albums. A comparison of detection rates achieved with Grounding DINO versus BLIP shows the advantage of the more powerful open set detection model: "man" was detected 2776 times by Grounding DINO, but only 1508 times by BLIP; "woman" 1641 times vs. 737; "cartoon" 743 times vs. 16; "leatherjacket" 461 times vs. 32; "suit" 375 times vs. 129.

In terms of their semantic meaning, the majority of detected objects are persons and their facial features: "man", "woman", "blondehair" and "beard". Another large group of detected objects are clothes and other attire: "leatherjacket", "suit", "hat", "dress", "glasses", "cowboyhat", "tie", "bikini" and "hoodie". Another notable group are music instruments: "guitar", "microphone", "trumpet" and "piano".

The analysis of frequent combinations of two and three classes, as shown in Table 4, revealed "man - woman" as the most common pairing, found in 6.07% of the albums. "Man - leather jacket" also appeared frequently, present in 5.60% of the albums. The trio "blonde hair - long hair - woman" was observed in 4.73% of the albums. Additionally, "man - suit" and "woman - dress" were seen in 3.74% and 2.84% of the albums, respectively. It is important to note that the frequency of appearance of these combinations in an image is counted uniquely, e.g., if an image

Class	Freq	%
man-woman	190	6.07
leatherjacket-man	175	5.59
blondehair-longhair-woman	148	4.73
man-suit	117	3.74
hat-man	110	3.51
leatherjacket-woman	108	3.45
blondehair-man	92	2.94
dress-woman	89	2.84
leatherjacket-man-suit	74	2.36
cowboyhat-hat-man	62	1.98

Table 4. Frequent combinations detected by Grounding DINO, showing absolute frequency (Freq) and percentage of Billboard dataset (%).

contains two instances of "man," it is counted as one occurrence to ensure more balanced results.

Figure 4 displays the top five object classes detected across 11 of the 31 genres (the 9 most frequent genres plus K-Pop and Latin). Both "man" and "woman" classes are consistently present across all genres. Metal albums show a higher occurrence of "cartoon" (30.3%), surpassing the "woman" class (21.3%). Additionally, 11.0% of Metal albums feature "skulls," an object very unique for this genre.

Figure 4. Most frequent objects detected per genre using Grounding DINO. The numbers in the figure present the absolute album count and the corresponding percentage within each category.

Figure 5. Most frequent objects detected per artist type using Grounding DINO. The numbers in the figure present the absolute album count and the corresponding percentage within each category.

For Show Tunes, "woman" appears in 34.4% of albums, and again uniquely, the class "dress" appears in 10.5% of albums within this genre only. In Pop and Soul genres, there is a higher prevalence of the "woman" class. In Pop, the classes "blonde hair" and "long hair" are also notable, each appearing in approximately 10.6% and 10.7% of albums, respectively, highlighting a specific depiction of women within these genres. Other genres exhibiting very unique class occurrences are Country, with 12.6% of albums showing the object "cowboy hat". In K-Pop 36.4% of the albums include the class "cartoon," significantly higher than other genres. This suggests a distinct visual style for K-POP albums as compared to Western music.

The analysis of the top five most frequent object classes detected per artist type, as detailed in Figure 5, shows interesting gender specific patterns. For bands and male solo artists, a significant number of albums feature the class "man" (40.5% for bands and 49.5% for male solo artists). However, the class "woman" also appears notably: 28.9% in albums for bands and 11.0% in albums by male artists. This could suggest a presence of female members or a mixed gender composition in bands, and for male solo artists it indicates that women often feature in the album artwork. In contrast, when examining the top classes for female artists, the class "man" does not appear among the top five. Instead, the classes "long hair" (16.2%), "dress" (10.8%), and "blonde hair" (14.7%) are more prevalent. This suggests that for female artists, the class "man" is not as commonly used as part of the album cover composition.

5. CONCLUSION

We presented a zero-shot object detection approach enabling a quantitative iconographic analysis of music album cover art. The processing pipeline consisted of automatic captioning to suggest candidate object keywords which were then used as input object classes to a state-of-the-art object detection model. This combination of bootstrapping object keywords followed by zero-shot object detection allowed high precision of more than 70% without any re-training of the detection model.

For the first time it was possible to analyze the number of objects and their mutual relations depicted in album covers in an automated quantitative way. This revealed a number of interesting results: the dominance of objects relating to the artists and their facial features as well as their attire; the commonness of depicted instruments and idiosyncratic objects for individual genres; gender specific combinations of objects like women appearing on album covers of male solo artists but not vice versa.

Future work could analyze temporal changes of depicted objects thereby allowing retracing of musical trends and acknowledging the shifting nature of musical concepts like genre [24]. The external validity [14] of our results could be tested by going beyond USA chart music including data from other countries and cultural backgrounds or by going beyond chart music including commercially less successful niche genres which might show more diverse cover artwork.

As a concluding thought, we hope that our work presented here is a convincing proof of concept showing that a quantitative approach based on machine learning is able to provide an iconography of album cover art work at large scale.

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